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Lamellar and pillared ZSM-5 zeolites modified with MgO and ZnO for catalytic fast-pyrolysis of eucalyptus woodchips

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Abstract

Lamellar and pillared ZSM-5 materials modified with Mg and Zn oxides were synthesized and tested for in-situ catalytic upgrading of eucalyptus woodchips fast-pyrolysis vapors. The introduction of silica pillars into the lamellar ZSM-5 support led to a higher BET area, but also reduced the overall catalyst acidity. The incorporation of MgO and ZnO occurred with a high dispersion over the zeolitic supports, causing also a significant reduction in the value of their textural properties due to a partial blockage of the zeolite pores. Likewise, the acid features of the zeolitic supports underwent sharp changes by the addition of both MgO and ZnO with a strong decrease in the concentration of the Brønsted and Lewis acid sites present in the parent zeolite, as detected by pyridine adsorption followed FTIR spectroscopy. However, additional Lewis acid sites were created associated to the metal oxides deposited onto the zeolitic supports.

Pyrolysis tests were accomplished using a lab-scale downdraft fixed-bed reactor working at atmospheric pressure and a temperature of 500 °C. The use of zeolitic

catalysts increased the gas yield, mostly due to the formation of CO and CO₂, to the detriment of bio-oil production. However, the so obtained bio-oils presented higher quality in terms of H/C and O/C ratios, and larger heating values. The incorporation of MgO and ZnO allowed tailoring the zeolite activity to avoid an excessive cracking of the bio-oil, which in turn resulted in a higher yield of the organic compounds present in the bio-oil, and decreasing the formation of undesired polyaromatic hydrocarbons and coke.

Keywords: lignocellulosic biomass, catalytic fast-pyrolysis, bio-oil, two-dimensional zeolite, ZSM-5

1. Introduction

The viability, sustainability, and overall commercial readiness of biofuels are still a matter of profound debate. While the potential benefits of replacing fossil fuels by liquids from renewable sources are obvious, substantial barriers for their implementation need still to be overcome [1]. In contrast to other renewable energies (e.g., wind, solar), supplying heat and power, biomass represents the only renewable resource of liquid, solid and gaseous fuels [2,3].

Lignocellulosic biomass is a mixture of cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin and minor amounts of other organic and inorganic species. Lignocellulose can be decomposed by means of pyrolysis working at different heating rates and temperatures, and following a variety of pathways [4]. Fast-pyrolysis, in which biomass is rapidly heated to relatively moderate temperatures (450-550 °C), followed by a fast quenching of vapors and aerosols (< 2 s of residence time), gives rise to three main product categories: solid char, non-condensable gases (H₂, CO, CO₂ and light hydrocarbons), and a dark brown liquid

phase (bio-oil). Non-catalytic fast-pyrolysis leads to a bio-oil consisting of a very complex mixture of oxygenated species derived from the fragmentation of the main components of the biomass. Unfortunately, high oxygen content (35-40 wt%) in biomass pyrolysis oil causes many undesirable properties regarding its potential application as fuel. Bio-oil contains between 15-30 wt% of water, it possesses a reduced calorific value and a high viscosity, is immiscible with gasoline and has acid pH (2-3) [5,6].

Catalytic upgrading of bio-oil is an interesting route for converting it into advanced biofuels, having properties very similar to conventional transportation fuels, although it requires an almost total deoxygenation of the bio-oil. This can be accomplished either by decoupling pyrolysis and bio-oil deoxygenation steps, or by integrated catalytic pyrolysis [7–10]. When pyrolysis vapors enter the pores of the catalyst they may undergo a complex series of reactions such as cracking, aromatization, ketonization, aldol condensation, isomerization, oligomerization and dehydrogenation, among others. Deoxygenation may occur removing water (dehydration), CO (decarbonylation) and CO₂ (decarboxylation). In addition, some carbon and hydrogen are lost by coke formation over the catalyst and the production of gaseous hydrocarbons as a consequence of cracking of the bio-oil vapors [5,7,9,11,12].

A variety of heterogeneous catalysts has been studied in the literature for their application in lignocellulosic biomass catalytic fast-pyrolysis or bio-oil upgrading [5,13–15]. In this respect, acidic zeolite catalysts, and in particular ZSM-5, have been commonly used for catalytic pyrolysis of biomass due to its high activity, as it has been recently reviewed by Liu et al. [5]. However, these materials are limited by the size of their micropores that can hinder the accessibility to the active sites and impede the

diffusion of large molecules into the pore system. To tackle this problem, recent advances have been achieved with the development of novel materials such as two-dimensional (2D) layered zeolites [16,17], which contain a high share of non-steric limited external surface area and a combination of micro- and mesopores. Recent achievements have shown that 2D zeolites can be synthesized not only via traditional bottom-up approach [18], but also via top-down treatment of appropriate germanosilicates [19,20]. Lee et al. [21] have studied the catalytic pyrolysis of biomass model constituents (cellulose, hemicelluloses and lignin) using unilamellar mesoporous ZSM-5, nanosheets (UMNs) and Al-SBA-15 catalysts. The results obtained denote the improvement of the bio-oil properties, which show lower oxygen content when UMN was used as catalyst due to its superior acid properties. Nevertheless, zeolites suffer of extensive coking and deactivation when used in lignocellulosic biomass catalytic pyrolysis because of its high acid strength.

On the other hand, base oxides have been employed as catalysts for ketonization and aldol condensation of carboxylic acids and other compounds possessing carbonyl groups [5], which could be applied in the deoxygenation of bio-oil by releasing CO₂ and the formation of C-C bonds. In this way, alkaline earth metal oxides such as MgO and CaO, where the oxide ions behave as bases and their metal cations could function as Lewis acids [22], have been recently used as biomass pyrolysis catalysts [23]. Likewise, transition metal oxides, such as ZnO, ZrO₂ and TiO₂, have been also investigated for the lignocellulose catalytic fast-pyrolysis in order to promote ketonization and aldol condensation reactions as a method for bio-oil upgrading [5,24,25].

The main goal of the present work is to establish the performance of novel catalysts for lignocellulose catalytic pyrolysis based on lamellar and pillared ZSM-5 (2D) zeolites,

featured by having a high accessibility due to the presence of a large share of external and mesopore surface area. Moreover, these zeolites have been here used as supports for the incorporation of MgO and ZnO in order to modify and tune their acidic properties and improve their catalytic behavior in bio-oil upgrading processes.

2. Experimental

2.1. Raw biomass

Eucalyptus woodchips were selected as lignocellulosic biomass to carry out the catalytic fast-pyrolysis experiments. This biomass belongs to the hardwoods type and contains 35.5, 12.5 and 39.2 wt% of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin, respectively. The sample was ground with a cutter mill and sieved to the desired particle size (0.5-1 mm). The proximate analysis of the sample was performed according to European standards. It included 9.7 wt% of moisture (UNE-EN 14774-1:2010), whereas the ash (UNE-EN 14775:2010), volatile matter (UNE-EN 15148:2010) and fixed carbon (determined by difference) contents, in dry basis, were 1.83, 74.70 and 23.47 wt%, respectively. In addition, the ultimate analysis of the eucalyptus sample was carried out in a micro-elemental analyzer (Thermo Scientific) in order to determine the content of C, H, N, S and O (the latter by difference); which, in dry and ash free basis, were 51.23, 5.93, 0.13, 0.00 and 42.71 wt%, respectively. A literature correlation [26] was employed to calculate the high heating value (HHV) of the dried eucalyptus sample, resulting a value of 20.04 MJ/kg.

2.2. Catalysts preparation

2.2.1. Synthesis of lamellar ZSM-5 (L-ZSM-5)

The synthesis of lamellar ZSM-5 is based on the procedure described by Choi et al. [27]. The structure directing agent (SDA) was prepared following the protocol detailed by Na et al. [28], but replacing 1-bromooctadecane by 1-bromodocosane (98%, TCI). The preparation of the gel, as well as the zeolite synthesis, were carried out in a 1000 ml stainless steel Parr 4848 autoclave with mechanical stirring. Thereby, 9.88 g of NaOH (99.5%, Penta, Czech Republic) were dissolved in 223 g of distilled water, followed by the addition of 5.91 g of $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 16 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (95%, Fluka). After dissolution, 6.47 g of sulphuric acid (96%, Penta, Czech Republic) and 86 g of tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS, 98%, Aldrich) were introduced into the mixture, being then stirred for 70 min. Thereafter, 30 g of the structure directing agent (SDA), a quarternary ammonium-type surfactant ($\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{45}\text{-N}^+(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{-N}^+(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{-C}_6\text{H}_{13}$) in bromide form ($\text{C}_{22-6-6}\text{Br}_2$) were added and the mixture so obtained was homogenized for another 30 min. Then, 35 g of water were added before closing the autoclave to compensate the ethanol evaporation, that is formed from TEOS hydrolysis. The final molar composition of the gel was $60 \text{ NaOH} \cdot 2.27 \text{ Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 16 \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 100 \text{ SiO}_2 \cdot 10 \text{ SDA} \cdot 3000 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$.

The zeolite crystallization proceeded under hydrothermal conditions at 155 °C, stirring (350 rpm) and autogeneous pressure for 144 h. The solid product was collected by filtration, washed out with distilled water and dried at 65 °C overnight. Then, it was calcined in air at 540 °C for 8 h. The calcined sample was ion-exchanged into the NH_4^+ form by treating four-times with 1.0 M NH_4NO_3 solution for 4 h at room temperature (100 ml of solution/1 g of zeolite) and calcined at 450 °C for 90 min to convert it into the protonic form. The final product was denoted as L-ZSM-5.

2.2.2. Synthesis of pillared ZSM-5 (PI-ZSM-5)

The as-synthesized dry lamellar ZSM-5, obtained according to the procedure described in the earlier section, was pillared using TEOS as pillaring agent [29]. For that purpose, 190 ml of TEOS were mixed with 18.8 g of L-ZSM-5 and stirred in a 250 ml flask at 85 °C for 20 h. The solid material was then separated by centrifugation and dried at ambient temperature for 36 h. The as-synthesized pillared material (31.8 g) was hydrolyzed in 2000 ml of water with the addition of 50 ml of ethanol at ambient temperature for 24 h. Finally, the material was filtered, dried at 65 °C overnight and calcined in air at 540 °C for 6 hours with a heating ramp of 2 °C/min. The calcined pillared ZSM-5 was ion-exchanged into NH_4^+ form by treating four-times with 1.0 M NH_4NO_3 solution for 4 hours at room temperature (100 ml of solution/1 g of zeolite) and calcined again at 450 °C for 90 min using a ramp of 2 °C/min to obtain the zeolite in H^+ form. The final product was denoted as PI-ZSM-5.

2.2.3. Mg and Zn oxide incorporation

10 wt% of MgO (or ZnO) were incorporated over the layered and pillared zeolites by wet impregnation method using ethanol as solvent. Initially, 50% of the total required metal precursor $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $[\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, both from Aldrich] was dissolved in 20 ml of ethanol and then, 2 g of support were added to this solution. The mixture was then left under stirring for 6 h at 40 °C. Subsequently, the solvent was removed in a rotary evaporator and the solid was dried overnight at 100 °C in an oven, being finally oven treated at 200 °C for 10 h. In a similar way, the second half of the metal precursor was incorporated to the material obtained and the resulting solid was finally calcined at 450 °C for 6 h.

2.3. Catalyst characterization

Metal contents of the samples were determined by ICP-OES on a Perkin Elmer Optima 7300 DV instrument. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analyses were collected on a Philips X'Pert PRO diffractometer operated at 45 kV and 40 mA with Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda=1.542$ Å). Argon physisorption isotherms at -186 °C were measured on a Quantachrome AUTOSORB iQ system. The surface area was determined using the Brunauer-Emmet-Teller (BET) equation and the pore size distributions were calculated by applying the NLDFT model to the adsorption branch of the isotherms. TEM images of the catalysts were obtained with a Philips TECNAI 20 instrument operating at 200 kV.

The acidic properties were determined by pyridine adsorption followed by FTIR spectroscopy. The samples were prepared as self-supporting wafers (ca. 8-12 mg/cm²) and activated overnight at 450 °C under vacuum prior to the adsorption of the probe molecule (pyridine) at 150 °C and a pressure of 3 torr. All spectra were recorded with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ in the 4000-400 cm⁻¹ range using a Nicolet spectrometer equipped with a MCT/B detector cooled with liquid nitrogen and normalized to a 10 mg/cm² wafer. The strength of the acid sites was studied by recording the FTIR spectra after treating the sample at different desorption temperatures (150, 250, 350 and 450 °C) for 20 min. The quantification of the acid sites was performed using the following bands (ν_{19b} vibration mode of pyridine) and absorption coefficients: pyridine PyH⁺ band at 1545 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=1.67$ cm/ μ mol) and pyridine PyL bands at 1461+1454 cm⁻¹ ($\epsilon=2.2$ cm/ μ mol) [30,31].

2.4. Biomass fast-pyrolysis tests

The schematic diagram of the lab-scale experimental setup used for the Eucalyptus woodchips fast-pyrolysis tests is shown in Fig. 1. It consists of a downdraft fixed-bed stainless steel reactor (16 mm i.d and 400 mm length) heated by two electrical furnaces. The reaction temperature is measured by two type K thermocouples, placed on the pyrolysis zone and inserted into the catalyst bed, respectively. The reactor is loaded with 1 g of catalyst, to operate with a biomass-to-catalyst ratio of 5 g/g. Previously to the pyrolysis tests, all the catalyst samples are pelletized, crushed and sieved to a particle size in the 180-250 μm range. The biomass sample is placed in the biomass tank and kept at room temperature. A quartz wool sheet and a metallic plate are placed over the catalyst particles to avoid the physical contact and possible mixing between the char particles and the catalyst bed. The pyrolysis tests have been carried out at atmospheric pressure and 500 °C. Prior to each pyrolysis experiment and during the heating up of the reactor, the biomass tank and all the reaction system are purged with a N₂ flow delivered by mass flow controllers, until the O₂ concentration levels of the exiting gas drop to < 0.1 vol.%, ensuring that pyrolysis takes place in an inert atmosphere. Once the reactor temperature reaches the desired set point, the feeding valve is open and the biomass falls into the reactor, being subjected to pyrolysis to form a solid carbonaceous residue (char) and vapours. The volatiles so generated are swept by a N₂ flow of 100 Nml/min and passed through the catalyst bed to leave rapidly the reaction zone, being condensed by means of an ice-water trap (0-4 °C). Permanent gases and light hydrocarbons (CH₄, C₂H₄, C₂H₆, C₃H₆ and C₃H₈) are finally collected in a sampling bag for their further analysis in a dual channel Agilent[®] CP-4900 Micro Gas Chromatograph (Micro-GC), which is equipped with molecular sieve (Molsieve 5 Å) and HayeSep A

columns and a thermal conductivity detector (TCD), using Helium as carrier gas. The TCD is periodically calibrated with a standard gas mixture containing N₂ (internal standard), O₂, H₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄, C₂H₄, C₂H₆, C₃H₆ and C₃H₈. Thus, the gas mass yield and its elemental composition (C, H and O) can be calculated.

After the experiments, the char and the used catalyst are collected for their further characterization. Char is characterized in the same way as the raw biomass, proximate and ultimate analyses being performed. In the case of the coke fraction, its amount is determined as the weight loss experienced by the used catalyst exposed in a TGA to a heating program of 10 °C/min up to 550 °C in air atmosphere.

Finally, the bio-oil is characterized by several techniques. For the catalytic fast pyrolysis tests, bio-oils are formed by two phases, being separated by centrifugation for further analysis. The water content of bio-oil is determined using a Karl-Fischer titration instrument (ASTM E203-08), whilst its elemental composition of C, H, N, S and O (by difference) is calculated with a Thermo-Scientific micro analyser. Thus, the bio-oil fraction is considered in a water free basis. Bio-oils were analysed by a Gas Chromatograph Mass Spectrometer, GC-MS, Bruker® SCION 436-GC, (Electron Energy 70eV, Emission 300V; He flow rate: 1 ml/min; Column WCOT fused silica 30 m x 0.25 mm ID x 0.25 µm). NIST EI-MS spectral library (v2.0) has been used for the compounds identification (with a minimum match score of 700). Bio-oil compounds are further grouped in families according to their main functional groups.

Finally, from the weight of the bio-oil and char fractions, and those calculated for coke and gas fractions, the total mass balance can be closed to the amount of biomass fed. The elemental (C, H and O) mass balances were also assessed from the yield of the different products and their ultimate analyses.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Catalyst properties

Six different catalysts have been prepared and investigated in the present work for catalytic pyrolysis of eucalyptus woodchips. They consist of two zeolitic supports (layered and pillared ZSM-5) and the corresponding samples after addition of 10 wt% of MgO and ZnO. These samples have been characterized by different techniques in order to determine the effect of the metal oxides incorporation on their physicochemical properties. The amounts of aluminum, as well as the final metal oxide loadings, were determined by ICP-OES (Table 1). PI-ZSM-5 presents a higher Si/Al ratio than L-ZSM-5 due to the introduction of silica pillars. The measured metal oxide loadings are quite close to the theoretical one added onto the zeolitic supports. In the case of the two samples containing Zn, the measured amount of the metal, expressed in the form of metal oxides, is somewhat higher (around 11 wt%) than the theoretical value. This result suggests that not all the Zn species are present solely as ZnO in the final catalysts.

Low-angle X-ray diffraction pattern (Fig. S1) of calcined L-ZSM-5 exhibits a reflection at $2\theta \approx 1.34^\circ$ ($d = 6.6$ nm) ascribed to the interlamellar structural correlation in the multilamellar ZSM-5 material [32]. After pillaring with TEOS the as-synthesized L-ZSM-5, it is appreciated a similar reflection at $2\theta \approx 1.39^\circ$ ($d = 6.4$ nm) for the calcined PI-ZSM-5, suggesting that the structural order of the lamellas have been retained by the introduction of silica pillars. These facts were corroborated by TEM analysis (Fig. S2), observing clear differences between both parent materials due to the presence of lamellas and pillars, respectively. High-angle XRD patterns are shown in Fig. 2. PI-ZSM-5 and L-ZSM-5 present diffraction lines typical of crystalline zeolites with MFI topology. It is also evident that after the incorporation of MgO and ZnO to the supports,

the catalysts still exhibit a very high crystallinity. It is important to highlight that no diffractions peaks corresponding to the pure metal oxides have been detected. This fact may be assigned to different factors: existence of MgO and ZnO particles with very small size, homogeneous dispersion of the metal oxides over the zeolitic support surface, or even, the partial ion exchange of protons of the support by Mg²⁺ and Zn²⁺ cations.

TEM measurements were also performed in order to get more information about the distribution of the metal oxides particles (Fig. S3). No particles or spots are observed in the micrographs that could correspond with MgO and ZnO phases. These results reinforce the idea of the metal oxides being present in the form of very-small entities with a high dispersion over the supports.

The textural properties of the catalysts were determined from argon physisorption isotherms at -186 °C (Fig. 3a and 3c). The pore size distributions were calculated in the whole range of micro- and mesopores by applying the NLDFT model (Fig. 3b and 3d). It is well known that conventional ZSM-5 zeolite presents a type I isotherm according to the IUPAC classification. However, the presence of multilamellar structures (in L-ZSM-5) and pillars (in PI-ZSM-5) strongly modifies the typical zeolitic profile. The isotherms of the different catalysts show three main regions of adsorption (Fig. 3): i) low pressures adsorption ($P/P_0 < 0.1$), which corresponds to the presence of micropores, ii) intermediate relative pressure adsorption, associated with adsorption on the external surface and the filling of mesopores and iii) adsorption at high pressures ($P/P_0 > 0.9$), which evidences the existence of interparticle voids.

Interestingly, the contribution of the mesopore+external surface area reaches very high values, 439 and 316 m²/g, for PI-ZSM-5 and L-ZSM-5 samples, respectively (Table 1),

denoting the relevance of the non-microporous textural properties in these materials. The profiles and values here obtained for the zeolitic supports are in agreement with those earlier reported for 2D ZSM-5 zeolites [32]. The high availability of mesopore+external surface areas in both L-ZSM-5 and PI-ZSM-5 is an important factor as it could enable good dispersions of the metallic oxide phases. Regarding the pore size distribution, both zeolitic supports exhibit a sharp peak centered at 5.5 Å characteristic of the ZSM-5 zeolite micropores. On the other hand, pillared ZSM-5 possesses a quite well defined adsorption jump at a relative pressure of 0.4-0.5, denoting the presence of a mesoporosity with a narrow pore size distribution centered at 40 Å (Fig. 3b). In contrast, the increase in the Ar adsorption at intermediate relative pressures is less pronounced for L-ZSM-5, evidencing the presence of an irregular array of the zeolite layers with a significant contribution of interlamellar voids (Fig. 3d) [27].

The incorporation of MgO and ZnO causes in all cases a strong decrease in the Ar adsorption in the whole range of relative pressures, suggesting that it affects strongly the support porosity. It is noticeable that the changes induced in the Ar isotherms by the metal addition are very close for both Mg and Zn, suggesting that they present quite similar dispersion and location over the zeolitic supports. The contribution of both micro- and mesopore peaks in the pore size distribution curves undergo a significant decrease (Figs. 3b and 3d). This result confirms that the deposition/incorporation of the metal species occurs and affects practically to all the support surface areas (micropore, mesopore and external surface areas), which can be also considered as another indication of their high dispersion onto the zeolitic support.

The values of the BET, mesopore+external and micropore surface areas, after the Mg and Zn addition, have been expressed in relation to those corresponding to the zeolitic

supports to gain further insights about the location of the metal oxides. In general, the textural properties (surface area and pore values) are clearly lower for the samples incorporating the metal oxides compared to the parent supports (Table 1). Thus, the PI-ZSM-5 sample has a BET surface area of 623 m²/g that decreases to values of 328 and 300 m²/g (referred to the weight of zeolitic support present in the catalyst) after the addition of MgO and ZnO, respectively. These figures correspond with about 50% of those determined in the parent supports. A strong reduction is also observed in this parameter for the lamellar based catalyst. The same occurs when analyzing the decrease observed in the mesopore+external surface area, showing values that represents about 50% of those determined for the parent L-ZSM-5 and PI-ZSM-5 samples. Likewise, the micropore surface area shows values of 177 and 184 m²/g for the parent zeolites (L-ZSM-5 and PI-ZSM-5, respectively), which decreases to reach the range 53 – 119 m²/g for the metal oxide – containing materials. The latter represents about 55 – 66% of the micropore surface area in the raw supports, although a higher micropore surface area reduction is observed for the ZnO/PI-ZSM-5, which could be related to an enhanced accessibility of the Zn species in micropores of the pillared zeolitic support.

The strong variations observed in the Ar isotherms, and in the corresponding textural properties, may be assigned to a combination of different phenomena: location of metal oxide species within the zeolite micropores, deposition of metal oxides particles on the mesopores blocking the entrance to the zeolite micropores and ion exchange of the protons in Si-OH-Al species by Mg²⁺ and Zn²⁺. Probably all of them take place simultaneously for the systems here studied.

The incorporation of metal oxides induces also substantial changes in the acidic properties of the parent zeolites. In order to evaluate the type, concentration and

strength of the acid sites, pyridine adsorption followed by FTIR was performed. As an alternative probe molecule, CO can be also employed. However, it has been reported that for layered MCM-22 and MCM-56 zeolites, the O–H frequency shift probed by an adsorbed weak base like CO is not a general indicator for ranking zeolite Brønsted acidity [33,34]

In the region corresponding to the stretching vibrations of hydroxyl groups (Fig. S4), the band located at 3745 cm^{-1} is assigned to terminal silanols (Si-OH), whereas the band at 3613 cm^{-1} is ascribed to acidic bridging hydroxyls groups (Si-OH-Al) [31]. These bands are clearly visible in the parent ZSM-5 zeolite samples (L-ZSM-5 and PI-ZSM-5). The vibrational band observed at 3613 cm^{-1} is more marked in the case of L-ZSM-5 due to its higher content of aluminum. This absorption band disappears in all cases with the incorporation of Mg and Zn evidencing the replacement/interaction between the zeolite protons and the metal species [35].

After adsorption of pyridine at $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Fig. 4) the bands associated to pyridinium ions (PyH⁺, pyridine chemisorbed on Brønsted acid sites) at 1545 cm^{-1} (ν_{19b}) and 1637 cm^{-1} (ν_{8a}) decrease in the samples containing Mg and Zn oxides. Coordinated pyridine species (PyL, pyridine interacting with Lewis acid sites) give rise to bands at $1464\text{-}1445\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_{19b}) and $1600\text{-}1628\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_{8a}). It must be noted that the higher are these wavenumbers, the stronger is the Lewis acidity [36]. The parent zeolites present bands at around 1456 cm^{-1} and 1623 cm^{-1} associated to pyridine strongly adsorbed on coordinatively unsaturated Al³⁺ ions. The latter vibration is mainly ascribed to pyridine interacting with Al³⁺ in tetrahedral environment [37]. On the other hand, the vibration band at 1444 cm^{-1} is due to the interaction between pyridine and silanols.

As it can be observed in Fig. 4, the spectra of the samples containing Mg and Zn species change noticeably compared to the parent supports, with a shifting of the peak at 1456 cm^{-1} towards lower frequencies (1448 cm^{-1} and 1454 cm^{-1} , respectively) due to their different polarizing power. The presence of these Lewis acid sites, with medium-strong strength is clearly related to the metal incorporation, being also evidenced by the appearance of new bands at 1610 cm^{-1} and 1613 cm^{-1} [38]. Interestingly, it seems that the incorporation of Mg and Zn species not only affects to the Brønsted acid sites but also to tri-coordinated aluminum in tetrahedral environment since the band at 1623 cm^{-1} decreases as well. This fact seems to be more pronounced in the case of Mg based materials.

Fig. 5 depicts the concentration of Brønsted and Lewis acids sites at different temperatures for all studied samples, referred to the weight of the zeolitic support. In general, it is observed that the amount of acid centers decreases with the temperature proving the existence of sites with different acid strength. Comparing both supports (PI-ZSM-5 and L-ZSM-5), the introduction of amorphous silica pillars decreases the concentration of Brønsted acid sites (Fig. 5a) in comparison with the lamellar samples (Fig. 5c), although quite smaller differences are found for Lewis acid sites. This is in agreement with the results provided by the ICP-OES measurements showing that the pillared zeolitic support presents a higher Si/Al ratio and suggests that the silica pillars contribute also to the Lewis acidity.

The incorporation of metal oxides sharply decreases the concentration of Brønsted acid sites for both lamellar and pillared zeolitic materials. Thus, in the case of PI-ZSM-5, the concentration of those sites, detected after pyridine desorption at 150 °C, is just about 21% of that present in the parent support for both Mg and Zn-containing materials.

Likewise, for the L-ZSM-5 sample, after the addition of Mg and Zn, only 18% and 33%, of the Brønsted acid sites contained in the raw support are now detected, respectively. It is quite evident that the reductions of the Brønsted acid sites concentration are quite superior than those above commented for the different surface areas of the supports (around 50% in most cases). Therefore, the acidity variations cannot be just assigned to the covering or blockage of the zeolite surface by the incorporated Mg and Zn phases, suggesting that a preferential interaction is established between the added metals and the zeolite Brønsted acid sites, probably by ion exchange with the protons of the latter. In this way, it must be taken into account that the Mg/Al and Zn/Al atomic ratios employed during the metal incorporation by impregnation ranges from 2 up to 10 depending on the metal and the support, being in all cases high enough for not discarding the contribution of ion-exchange phenomena.

Regarding the Lewis acid sites, the incorporation of Mg and Zn leads to an important increase in the overall concentration of this type of acid sites in comparison with the corresponding parent zeolitic materials (Figs. 5b and 5d). This fact, together with the shift observed in the position of the IR band originated by the adsorption of pyridine on Lewis acid sites, suggests that the incorporation of Mg and Zn oxides causes the generation of additional Lewis acid sites, probably related to the metal oxide particles. In order to distinguish between Lewis acid sites of the zeolitic support and those originated from the metal oxides, a deconvolution of the IR spectra in the region at 1650-1580 cm^{-1} has been performed. Thereby, the following bands have been considered for the supports: 1637 cm^{-1} (associated to pyridine bonded to Brønsted acid sites), 1623 cm^{-1} and $\sim 1615 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (both ascribed to pyridine adsorbed on coordinatively unsaturated Al^{3+} ions but probably of different strength and/or environments [37] –

Lewis acidity). Taking into account the areas for the latter two bands, and assuming that the proportion between them is the same in the region of 1456 cm^{-1} (used for quantification), it is possible to differentiate their contributions to the total amount of acid sites. In the case of the samples containing metal oxides, in addition to the bands at 1637 cm^{-1} and 1623 cm^{-1} (coming from the support), new bands at 1610 cm^{-1} and 1613 cm^{-1} were identified in presence of Mg and Zn species, respectively. Thus, the contribution of the signals at 1623 cm^{-1} and in the range $1616\text{-}1605\text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been calculated considering the different band areas of the parent zeolites and the metal oxide – containing materials as well as their total concentration of Lewis acid sites. The results so obtained are shown in Figs. 5b and 5d, distinguishing two zones in the bars. The one marked with thick patterns in this figure indicates the contribution of the band at 1623 cm^{-1} to the total Lewis acidity and the zone having a thin pattern is associated to the bands in the region $1616\text{-}1605\text{ cm}^{-1}$. While for the parent zeolitic supports, the 1623 cm^{-1} signal is predominant, a very important contribution of the latter bands is observed when incorporating Mg and Zn species. This is consistent with the presence of Lewis acid sites directly related to the metal oxide phases. The concentration of Lewis acid sites present in the parent zeolitic supports is also affected by the incorporation of Mg and Zn, although in a lower extension than that earlier commented for the Brønsted acid sites. This fact denotes that this type of acidity is less prone to interact with the Mg and Zn species than in the case of the Brønsted acid sites.

In the case of the Mg-containing zeolite samples, when increasing the pyridine desorption temperature up to $450\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, they present a lower overall concentration of Lewis acid sites than the parent PI-ZSM-5 and L-ZSM-5 materials. This result evidences that the new Lewis acid sites are weaker compared to those of the zeolitic

supports, as it was expected taking into account the observed absorption band shift towards lower wavenumbers (1448 cm^{-1}) after the Mg incorporation. For the ZnO/PI-ZSM-5 and ZnO/L-ZSM-5 samples, although the Lewis acid sites concentration is also strongly reduced when increasing the pyridine desorption temperature, they are still present at $450\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in similar or even slightly higher concentration of Lewis acid sites than the corresponding supports. This result agrees well with the Lewis sites band shift observed for the Zn-containing materials (1454 cm^{-1}), which is quite less pronounced than in the case of the samples incorporating Mg oxide.

It can be concluded from these measurements, that the incorporation of Mg and Zn phases causes strong changes in the acidic features of the layered and pillared ZSM-5 zeolites, suppressing in a great extension the Brønsted acidity and generating new types of Lewis acid sites. These changes are expected to have a significant role in the catalytic behavior of these materials for the lignocellulose catalytic fast pyrolysis.

3.2. Catalytic activity

Biomass pyrolysis produces three main product fractions: solid char, gases and a complex liquid mixture called bio-oil. When the vapours coming from biomass pyrolysis are put into contact with a catalyst, an important variation in the relative proportion of these fractions takes place, as well as the formation of another one, corresponding to the coke deposited on the catalyst. The results obtained in the present work for non-catalytic and catalytic fast-pyrolysis of eucalyptus woodchips are illustrated in Fig. 6 in the form of mass yield of the different fractions. In addition, Table 2 provides additional information about the composition and properties of the gas and bio-oil products.

Char is an important by-product of the pyrolysis process that may contain a significant proportion of the chemical energy in the feed material [39]. The minimum char yield, in dry basis, should be at least equal to the sum of the fixed carbon and ash contents of the raw biomass (25.3 wt%). Since the reaction system comprises two separated reaction zones (non-catalytic and catalytic), and the catalyst bed is downstream placed regarding the first pyrolysis zone, the type of catalyst does not affect nor modify the char formation. Accordingly, the char yield obtained in the different experiments is very similar, with random variations regarding an average value around 30 wt%. This figure confirms the relevance in quantitative terms of the char. Moreover, taking into account its elemental composition (relatively low oxygen content) and heating value, it can be easily concluded that the char accounts for more than 40% of the chemical energy contained in the initial biomass. Therefore, in order to have a feasible process, the char so produced should find specific applications instead of being considered just a residue of the pyrolysis process. Thus, it could be burnt for providing most of the energy consumed in the overall process, avoiding the use of external energy sources and making the process energy self-sufficient [36, 37]. Likewise, char gasification could be another interesting alternative for producing synthesis gas and/or hydrogen.

In addition to char, coke is formed in significant amounts in all cases over the different catalysts here investigated. In the case of the pure zeolitic catalysts (L-ZSM-5 and PI-ZSM-5), coke yield is about 3 wt% of the total raw biomass, which represents 15 wt% referred to the catalyst weight. This is a high amount for a catalyst based on ZSM-5 zeolite, suggesting that it is formed, at least in a great extension, outside the zeolite micropores. The incorporation of MgO, and particularly of ZnO, to the supports causes some reduction in the amount of coke, which can be considered a consequence of the

lower concentration of zeolite Brønsted and Lewis acid sites and the generation of a new Lewis acidity with a lower acid strength, in the metal oxide – containing catalysts.

Non-catalytic pyrolysis of eucalyptus woodchips produces about 12 wt% of gases, formed mainly by CO and CO₂, as well as by minor amounts of C₁-C₃ hydrocarbons. Catalytic fast-pyrolysis markedly increased the total gas yield up to values in the range 20-24 wt%, which is related to the enhanced deoxygenation produced in the catalytic tests through decarboxylation and decarbonylation. The second one seems clearly favoured when using both the zeolitic supports, as well as for the catalysts incorporating MgO, since the CO production is enhanced by a factor of around 2 (Table 2). In contrast, the addition of ZnO to the zeolitic supports causes also an important increase in the CO₂ yield, suggesting that this system promotes the decarboxylation pathway. On the other hand, all the catalysts display significant cracking activity of the pyrolysis vapours, increasing the production of gaseous hydrocarbons. This enhancement is particularly important in the case of gaseous olefins, although no clear trend is observed among the different catalysts. It is also noticeable that the hydrogen concentration in the gas stream undergoes a ten-fold increase when using ZnO-containing catalysts.

Water is other major product of biomass pyrolysis. In addition to the humidity that may be present in the raw biomass, water comes from a variety of dehydration reactions undergone by the starting biomass components or by primary and secondary pyrolysis products. Water is recovered as a component of the bio-oil fraction. Depending on the water amount, type and polarity of the organic components in bio-oil and even on the storage conditions, a phase separation may occur, so in this case the bio-oil consists really of two phases: aqueous and organic ones. In the experiments here reported, water has been detected in both of them, showing that a liquid-liquid equilibrium is really

established between both liquid phases rather than occurring a total segregation of the different components. Karl-Fisher analyses of these two phases indicate that their water content is very different with values of 69-75 wt% and 10-15 wt%, for the so called “aqueous” and “organic” phases, respectively. This is a fact to be carefully considered when comparing and discussing bio-oil yields, since the presence of different water contents may lead to not completely consistent conclusions. For this reason, in the present work water and bio-oil yields are given independently, so just the organic components are considered when using bio-oil yield data. The overall water produced in the non-catalytic test was 15.5 wt%, being increased when using catalysts up to 16.7-18.7 wt%, which shows that the different catalysts also promote in some extension dehydration reactions.

In order to get further insights about the different deoxygenation pathways, the selectivity towards dehydration, decarbonylation and decarboxylation has been represented in Fig 7. The predominant pathway in the case of the non-catalytic pyrolysis is dehydration with selectivity values around 64%, followed by decarboxylation and finally decarbonylation [40]. For the catalytic fast-pyrolysis test, the contribution of dehydration declines, reaching values of c.a. 53-55%, whereas decarbonylation and, in a lesser extension, decarboxylation are more favoured undergoing important selectivity enhancements regarding the non-catalytic pyrolysis. Compared to the zeolitic supports, the incorporation of MgO and, in special, of ZnO increases the decarboxylation selectivity. Therefore, it can be postulated that decarboxylation reactions are catalysed in a great part by Lewis acid sites. Taking into account, the gaseous fraction composition (Table 2), the behaviour of the ZnO-containing catalysts can be explained by the occurrence of the water gas shift reaction, that leads to the formation of CO₂ and

H₂ by reaction between CO and water. ZnO-based systems are well known to catalyze this reaction [41,42].

On the other hand, the data in Table 2 indicates that the incorporation of zeolitic catalysts to the process causes a significant reduction of the bio-oil yield (in a water free basis) from about 42 wt% to 24-30 wt%. This reduction was in a great part due to the oxygen removal as the bio-oil undergoes extensive deoxygenation over the catalysts, which in turn implies an improvement of its quality as fuel. This fact is also reflected in the high heating value of the bio-oil, which increases from 23.4 up to 27-31 MJ/kg for non-catalytic and catalytic fast-pyrolysis experiments, respectively. Fig. 8 compares the bio-oil yield (excluding the water content) obtained with the different catalysts investigated in this work, confirming the decrease produced in regard to the non-catalytic bio-oil. In addition to deoxygenation reactions, coke deposition and cracking to gaseous hydrocarbons also contribute to the bio-oil yield reduction. While the non-catalytic bio-oil is recovered as a complex mixture without phase segregation, two phases were observed and could be separated in all the catalytic fast-pyrolysis experiments. This is a consequence of both the higher water content of the latter and the larger deoxygenation degree of the organics in the liquid phase since both factors facilitate the separation of the aqueous and organic phases. No significant variations are observed in the yield of the organics present in the aqueous phase, which suggests that this parameter is determined and limited by the water solubility of the organic compounds. However, important differences can be seen in the yield of organic compounds in the organic phase. In this case, the highest yields are obtained with the MgO-containing catalysts, which is consistent with the lower deoxygenation degree obtained with them. As it was shown above, the incorporation of Mg species onto the

zeolitic catalysts causes drastic changes in their acidic features, strongly decreasing the concentration of both zeolitic Brønsted and Lewis acid sites. At the same time, the new generated acid sites, associated to MgO, exhibit a weak strength. All together confirm that the Mg-containing catalysts show the weakest acidity and, therefore, the lowest bio-oil deoxygenation activity.

Fig. 9 provides semi-quantitative information about the bio-oil composition based on the results obtained by GC-MS analyses for the non-catalytic and catalytic fast-pyrolysis tests. Aqueous and organic phases of the catalytic bio-oils were separately analyzed to determine the distribution of the different compound families in both phases, classified according to eight groups: carboxylic acids (AC), aldehydes (ALD), alcohols (ALC), ketones and ethers (KET & ETH), furans (FUR), aromatic hydrocarbons (AR), sugars (SUG) and oxygenated aromatics (O-AR), in addition to the group representing non-identified or unknown compounds (UNK). It must be noted that a critical bottleneck in studying catalytic fast-pyrolysis process is the fact that many bio-oil products cannot be identified with accuracy due to significant fragmentations in EI-MS and/or their absence in the database [43,44].

As seen in Fig. 9, non-catalytic fast-pyrolysis bio-oil mostly consists of oxygenated aromatics, 44%, (trimethoxy-toluene 6.7%, syringol 6.4%, trimethoxy-benzene 6.3%, creosol 3.2% and guaiacol 3.1%); followed by carboxylic acids, 15%, (acetic acid 14.4%); sugars, 11.6%, (levoglucosan 11%); ketones and ethers, 11.5% (acetol 5%) and furans, 8.2% (furfural 6.1%). Acetic acid is the most abundant single compound, which confers bio-oil corrosiveness and makes difficult its use as a fuel in engines [45].

In the case of bio-oils obtained by catalytic fast-pyrolysis, the aqueous phase consists mainly of acids (acetic acid), ketones (acetol) and ethers (1,1,1-trimethoxyethane),

whilst the organic phase contains most of the high molecular weight lignin-derived oxygenated aromatics 65-75%, (1,2,4-trimethoxybenzene, syringol and 3,4,5-trimethoxytoluene) and all the aromatic hydrocarbons. At a first glance (Fig. 9), the product distribution in the bio-oils is very different for non-catalytic and catalytic fast-pyrolysis experiments. Thus, the concentration of acetic acid, furans and sugars are significantly lower when the bio-oil vapours enter into contact with the catalysts.

Acetic acid conversion could follow direct deoxygenation pathways (decarbonylation and decarboxylation), as well as ketonization reactions, which would be consistent with the increase of the ketone concentrations observed with most of the catalysts. Ketonization of carboxylic acids has been reported to be promoted by both basic [46,47] and acid [48] catalysts. This reaction is of high interest in the system here studied as it allows the carboxylic acids concentration to be reduced, removing oxygen in the form of CO₂ and leading to the formation of C-C bonds.

Levogluconan is the most important compound derived directly from cellulose decomposition, which is detected in the biomass fast-pyrolysis oil. Interestingly, this compound completely reacted in the case of L-ZSM-5, PI-ZSM-5 and ZnO/L-ZSM-5 catalysts, being not observed in any of the two bio-oil phases. In the rest of the catalysts, levogluconan was also decomposed at a large extent, and only a small amount was detected in the aqueous phase. According to Mihalcik et al. [13], levogluconan is deoxygenated in two steps, in the first one dehydration to form furans occurs, and then conversion of the latter into aromatic hydrocarbons via consecutive dehydration and decarboxylation reactions. Cheng and Huber [49] and Dorado et al. [50] have shown the importance of Diels-Alder condensation and dehydration reactions of furan rings with

alkenes (ethylene or propylene) to produce aromatics (benzene, toluene, xylene, etc.) and water over ZSM-5 zeolite [49].

According to the results obtained in the present work, furfural accounts for 6.1 % of the non-catalytic bio-oil, being catalytically converted into furans and CO. Parent zeolites were the most effective catalysts producing aromatic hydrocarbons from the oxygen-rich vapors, increasing the aromatics proportion in the total bio-oil from 1.4 to 11.9 and 7.5% in case of L-ZSM-5 and PI-ZSM-5, respectively. Among aromatic hydrocarbons, the most abundant compounds were styrene, xylene, methyl-styrene, trimethyl-benzene; but also some polyaromatics hydrocarbons (PAHs) like methyl-naphthalene and dimethyl-naphthalene. PAHs are considered hazardous for the environment, and therefore disliked compounds among bio-oil components [11,51,52]. The incorporation of MgO and ZnO to both zeolitic supports decreases the overall production of aromatic hydrocarbons in favour of oxygenated aromatics, decreasing as well the formation of undesired PAHs [53–55]. Moreover, the latter are considered to be coke precursors, causing the catalyst deactivation [53,56,57]. As above denoted, the incorporation of ZnO and MgO into the zeolitic supports modifies strongly their acid features, increasing the Lewis acid sites to the detriment of Bronsted acid sites, which also contributes to a lower coke formation.

4. Conclusions

The in-situ upgrading of eucalyptus woodchips fast-pyrolysis vapors has been investigated over lamellar and pillared ZSM-5 catalysts, modified by impregnation with MgO and ZnO. XRD and TEM measurements indicate that the metal oxides are present in the form of very-small entities with a high dispersion over the supports.

The incorporation of MgO and ZnO causes in all cases a strong decrease in the Ar adsorption in the whole range of relative pressures, confirming that it affects strongly to the support porosity. As a result, the values of the textural properties (surface area and pore values) are significantly lower for the samples incorporating the metal oxides compared to the parent supports. The large decrease in both the zeolite micropore volume and surface after the addition of the metal oxides may be assigned to different phenomena: location within the zeolite micropores, deposition on the mesopores blocking the entrance to the zeolite micropores and introduction by ion exchange of the protons in Si-OH-Al species by Mg^{2+} and Zn^{2+} . Likewise, the incorporation of Mg and Zn phases causes strong changes in the acidic features of the layered and pillared ZSM-5 zeolites, suppressing in a great extension the Brønsted and Lewis acidity of the parent zeolites and generating new types of Lewis acid sites, with weaker strength and associated to the metal oxides.

The char yield obtained in the different experiments of eucalyptus woodchips fast pyrolysis is very similar, with random variations around an average value of 30 wt%, accounting for more than 40% of the chemical energy contained in the initial biomass. Therefore, in order to have a feasible process, the char so produced should find specific applications instead of being considered just a residue of the pyrolysis process.

Water is recovered as a component of the bio-oil fraction. Depending on the water amount, type and polarity of the organic components in the bio-oil and even on the storage conditions, a phase separation may occur, so in this case the bio-oil consists really of two phases: aqueous and organic ones. In the experiments here reported, water has been detected in both of them, with values of 69-75 wt% and 10-15 wt% for the so called “aqueous” and “organic” phases, respectively.

Regarding the organic compounds contained in the bio-oil, the incorporation of zeolitic catalysts to the process causes a significant reduction of the bio-oil yield (in a water free basis) from 42 to 24-30 wt%. This reduction is in a great part due to the oxygen removal as the bio-oil undergoes extensive deoxygenation over the catalyst, which in turn implies an improvement of its quality as fuel. This fact is also reflected in the high heating value of the bio-oil, which increases from 23.4 up to 27-31 MJ/kg for non-catalytic and catalytic fast-pyrolysis experiments, respectively.

Likewise, drastic variations are also observed when using the different catalysts in the product distribution per type of organic compounds present in the bio-oil. The concentration of carboxylic acids (formed mainly by acetic acid) decreases, leading to an enhancement in the ketone production. Moreover, sugar derivatives are almost completely transformed in the catalytic fast-pyrolysis tests, whereas furanic compounds also undergo extensive conversion. Both factors lead to the production of large amounts of both oxygenated aromatic compounds and aromatic hydrocarbons. MgO and ZnO incorporation into both lamellar and pillared supports, moderate the formation of aromatic hydrocarbons in favour of oxygenated aromatics due to the reduction caused by these metals in the concentration of strong zeolitic acid sites. This fact is of relevance as it affects positively the coke formation on the catalyst and prevents the formation of undesired polyaromatic hydrocarbons.

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